

22RPT03 MultiFixRad

D6 - Report on the comparisons of the newly developed temperature scale realisations against ITS-90 over the range 1000 °C to 2500 °C

RISE

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Glossary

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1 Summary

This report describes the efforts by some project partners to directly compare the newly developed temperature scale realisations with existing implementations of the ITS-90. Above the freezing point of silver (1235 K) the ITS-90 is realised using Planck's law in the ratio form, using a blackbody at the freezing point of pure Ag, Au or Cu as its reference temperature, i.e. it prescribes an extrapolation from a single fixed point. As a consequence, ITS-90 requires detailed knowledge of the pyrometer, in particular its linearity, and only a few of the participants currently have suitable equipment. Less experienced NMIs/DIs who did not have the ITS-90 scale realisation capability, worked with project participants which employed existing pyrometric implementations of the ITS-90. The comparisons were performed from 960 °C to 2500 °C, but with specific ranges for each participant as detailed in the activity descriptions.

RISE, SMU, CMI and Tübitak had equipment to realise the ITS-90. In this work, SMU compared their fixed point based scale to both the CMI and their own implementation of the ITS-90, Tübitak compared with their own implementation of the ITS-90, while DFM and JV compared their scales to the ITS-90 implementation at RISE.

2 Interlaboratory comparison at RISE between DFM, JV and RISE

The emerging nordic partners from JV and DFM developed interpolating pyrometers during the project and realised T at the respective institutions. An interlaboratory comparison campaign with the ITS-90 scale realised at RISE was conducted in February 2026.

The calibration of the pyrometers was based on different set of references. The JV calibration was based on the MultiFixRad created fixpoints Fe-C and Pd-C, while the DFM realisation was only based on extrapolation from the DFM silver fixpoint. Following the measurement campaign DFM realised Pd-C and Co-C fixpoint in collaboration with DTU but this was not included in this measurement campaign.

RISE setup

The RISE setup for the ILC was the Thermo Gauge 1-zone, graphite tube/heater. A custom Ø5 mm graphite cavity (see Figure 2.1) with a conical bottom is used as a reference blackbody. A piece of graphite insulation foam is placed behind the blackbody, and the reference pyrometer is aimed at the back to control the temperature of the oven.

Figure 2.1: Technical drawings of the graphite reference blackbody.

To measure the radial gradients at the bottom of the cavity, the LP5 was moved horizontally, perpendicular to the cavity, in steps of 0,5 mm and measured the temperature in each position for 30 seconds. The lowest temperature was found in the centre of the cavity bottom, with increasing temperatures towards the edges, as can be seen in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2: Transversal temperature gradient across the bottom of the cavity.

The emissivity of the reference blackbody was studied extensively. The high-end performance of the RISE LP5 enables detailed measurements of the blackbody emissivity, and numerical modelling using the software STEEP, of the blackbody emissivity was combined with measurements. 4 small holes were drilled in the sidewall of the blackbody cavity, and the emission was measured using precise increments in the hole depth to determine the axial temperature gradients in the black body. The results from the measurements can be seen below in Figure 2.3 and the effective emissivity from the numerical model in Figure 2.4, with numerical values in Table 2.1 Table 2.2.

Figure 2.3: Measured temperature gradient in the graphite blackbody cavity.

Figure 2.4: The modelled cavity bottom effective emissivity for the 3 relevant wavelength bands.

Cavity bottom temperature [°C]	650 nm Radiance temperature [°C]	800 nm Radiance temperature [°C]	940 nm Radiance temperature [°C]
957.85	962.74	961.76	961.12
1096.85	1103.54	1102.21	1101.35
1294.85	1304.73	1302.79	1301.53
1392.85	1404.08	1401.88	1400.46
1491.85	1504.24	1501.81	1500.25
1589.85	1605.05	1602.08	1600.17
1687.85	1705.57	1702.12	1699.90
1785.85	1805.84	1801.95	1799.46

Table 2.1: Radiance temperature from numerical model.

Cavity bottom temperature [°C]	650 nm Effective emissivity	800 nm Effective emissivity	940 nm Effective emissivity
957.85	1.0040	1.0032	1.0027
1096.85	1.0049	1.0039	1.0033
1294.85	1.0063	1.0051	1.0043
1392.85	1.0067	1.0054	1.0046
1491.85	1.0070	1.0056	1.0048
1589.85	1.0082	1.0066	1.0055
1687.85	1.0090	1.0073	1.0061
1785.85	1.0097	1.0078	1.0066

Table 2.2: Effective emissivity from numerical model.

Measurement setup

An optical table setup was developed for the purpose of the ILC, and precise mechanical stages were prepared for the 3 pyrometer setups. A rail mounted perpendicular to the oven access axis, together with a stop on the table, enabled very reproducible positioning of the 3 setups, and the mount was fastened to the optical table using an M6 screw for every measurement using the 3 setups. The 3 pyrometers mounted on the rail in front of the furnace can be seen in Figure 2.5.

The alignment of the setups was performed using the procedures of the partners, and the focus length was optimised for each.

Figure 2.5: Comparison setup at RISE between the DFM, JV and RISE pyrometers.

RISE measurement results

The measurements were taken in the following order: 962 °C, 1100 °C (2 cycles), 1300 °C, 1500 °C, 1700 °C, 1800 °C, 1600 °C, 1400 °C and 1100 °C.

After furnace stabilisation, the temperature was measured with the LP5 for at least 10 minutes. Then the DFM and JV devices respectively was moved into position for measurements, and finally the LP5 was moved into position for a measurement to check the temperature stability.

In Table 2.3 below, the following data is presented: (i) temperature mean value, which is the mean value of the 10 minutes initial measurement and the check measurement at the end; (ii) temperature stddev, which is the standard deviation for the 10 minutes initial measurement; (iii) temperature difference before-after, which is the difference of the mean value for the 10 minutes initial measurement and the mean value for the check measurement at the end.

All measurements are corrected regarding SSE and emissivity.

Nominal Temperature [°C]	Temperature mean value [°C]	Temperature stddev [mK]	Temperature difference before-after [mK]	Expanded uncertainty (k=2) [°C]
962	962,13	14	14	0,39
1100	1098,20	53	-55	0,40
1100	1102,65	23	-39	0,40
1100	1102,67	19	3	0,40
1300	1300,03	15	24	0,53
1400	1398,92	34	11	0,64
1500	1498,82	27	-68	0,68
1600	1599,99	32	-7	0,77
1700	1698,80	34	-9	0,85
1800	1798,15	69	29	0,93

Table 2.3: Temperatures measured by RISE with the LP5 pyrometer.

2.1 DFM comparison at RISE

DFM device

The DFM device is a camera-based pyrometer using an 800 nm +/- 20 nm bandpass filter, temperature stabilisation, and calibration to perform as a high-end pyrometer. An imaging system based on two 75 mm lenses and a 300 µm pinhole is created with an effective focusing length of 600 mm.

Filter characteristics

The transmission filter was measured using the DFM radiometer calibration facilities and is shown in Figure 2.6 below.

Figure 2.6: Filter transmission curve.

Using the quantum efficiency of the camera CCD and the measured filter transmission, the characteristic wavelength is found to be 800.51 nm and $\sigma = 11.62$ nm. This corresponds to Sakuma-Hattori parameters of $A = 799.4955$ nm and $B = 1.5167$ mK

Size of source

The size of the source, SSE, is determined for the DFM pyrometer using the direct method. For the data shown here, an SSE of 0.997 is measured for an aperture of $\varnothing 3$ mm, and 0.999 for the $\varnothing 5$ mm. This is limiting the usefulness as the uncertainty of the SSE and aperture size contributes too much to the uncertainty. This has been improved at the time of writing by changing to a 150 mm focal length imaging system.

Emissivity

The RISE blackbody is a custom graphite cavity with a conical bottom. Extensive modelling and measurements have been done at RISE to determine the effective emissivity.

An estimated value of 1.0032 for 958 °C and 1.0073 for 1688 °C was calculated for the 800 nm effective wavelength of the DFM pyrometer. An average value of effective cavity emissivity of 1.005 was chosen for the data presented, and the uncertainty included in the uncertainty budget.

The emissivity of the RISE Palladium-Carbon fixpoint was modelled to be 0.9998 with a $\varnothing 5$ mm diameter cavity and a 34.1 mm in length graphite cavity.

The emissivity of the DFM silverpoint was modelled using ray tracing calculation to 0.9996 due to the $\varnothing 9$ mm in diameter and 50 mm in length graphite cavity.

2.2 Monte-Carlo simulation of uncertainty

The standard uncertainty for the parameters is set to:

$U_{\lambda_0} = 0.0141$ nm, $U_{\sigma} = 0.000141$ nm

From the relative Sakuma-Hattori equation with $n = 1$, using the silver fixpoint, a Monte Carlo simulation of the uncertainty propagation was performed, and the results can be seen in Figure 2.7.

Figure 2.7: Calibration temperature uncertainty from Monte-Carlo simulation.

2.3 Measurements

Using the silver fixpoint and using the n=1 extrapolation scheme, the measurements shown in Table 2.4 below was performed.

Time	Measurement	Temperature [°C]	Pyrometer reading [°C]	Difference [°C]
10:37	0,0587055	962,200	962,45	-0,247
17:14	0,2479376	1098,400	1098,56	-0,164
11:24	0,2588905	1102,900	1103,08	-0,180
11:39	0,2588114	1102,900	1103,11	-0,212
12:44	1,3318422	1300,500	1300,84	-0,338
16:26	2,6145251	1399,600	1399,79	-0,192
13:30	4,7909357	1499,700	1499,86	-0,162
15:50	8,2803030	1601,200	1601,13	0,066
14:23	13,3918367	1700,300	1700,16	0,144
Palladium-Carbon fixpoint	4,554041	1491,200	1491,32	-0,123

Table 2.4: Temperature measurements at RISE by DFM.

The measurements of the cavity shown in Figure 2.8 below shows a clear deviation from the measurements at DFM.

Figure 2.8: Measured temperature deviation using the DFM pyrometer.

The fix of the ITS-90 realisation at DFM is the silver fixpoint. It was compared to the RISE silverpoint in 2023, showing a deviation of 0,017 K \pm 1 mK using the LP5 pyrometer at RISE.

2.4 JV comparison at RISE

2.5 Justervesenets device

The pyrometer was calibrated using the two-point scheme, with Fe-C and Pd-C as the calibration points. The signals were corrected for the emissivity of the cavities, and the transition temperatures lowered by the cavity wall heat loss due to radiation through the cavity opening into the ambient temperature. The signal is also

reduced by a factor 0.003 taken from an estimate of the SSE. The measured SSE curve is shown in Figure 2.9 below.

Figure 2.9: The SSE measure of the JV pyrometer.

Furnace effect and furnace gradients during the realisation are included in the uncertainty budget. Uncertainty due to noise is taken into account by first fitting a 3rd order polynomial to the melting curve to identify the point of inflection, and then the uncertainty in the attribution is computed from the fitting uncertainty at the point of inflection. The uncertainty from this has probably been exaggerated here.

A Monte-Carlo simulation computation of the resulting calibration uncertainty ($k=1$) is shown in Figure 2.10.

Figure 2.10: Calibration uncertainty ($k=1$) for the JV realisation.

2.6 Justervesenets measurements

The measurement results for JV are summarised in Table 2.5 below. The table contains the reported values from measurements, after correcting for the SSE.

Nominal	Temperature (SSE corrected)	Temperature (emissivity + SSE corrected)	Temperature std	Calibration uncertainty, JV, k=1
962	962,75	962,48	0,085	0,26
962	962,81	962,54	0,091	0,26
1100	1099,30	1098,88	0,046	0,20
1100	1103,78	1103,36	0,040	0,20
1100	1103,81	1103,39	0,037	0,20
1300	1301,61	1300,91	0,019	0,14
1400	1400,67	1399,82	0,019	0,16
1500	1500,90	1499,91	0,015	0,22
1600	1602,43	1601,13	0,019	0,31
1700	1701,41	1699,83	0,027	0,42
1800	1801,36	1799,48	0,012	0,54

Table 2.5: Summary of JV temperature measurements. All temperatures are given in °C.

In addition, a check was performed at the Pd-C fixed point. JVs pyrometer recorded a plateau of RISEs Pd-C fixed point on site. The result was a difference of 23 mK. The cell designs are identical, but the furnaces used are very different and one would expect that the 23 mK difference is one data point describing the hard-to-quantify furnace effect, although there could be small contributions from drift in transportation between Oslo and Borås, and the different furnace gradients as well.

2.7 Comparison JV, DFM, RISE

The measurements from JV and DFM are collected in Table 2.6 below.

RISE [°C]	JV [°C]	DFM [°C]	Diff JV-RISE [°C]	Diff DFM-RISE [°C]	Diff JV-DFM [°C]
962,12	962,48		0,35		
962,12	962,54	962,45	0,41	0,32	0,09
1098,22	1098,88	1098,56	0,68	0,37	0,32
1102,67	1103,36	1103,08	0,70	0,43	0,28
1102,67	1103,39	1103,11	0,72	0,44	0,28
1300,02	1300,91	1300,84	0,87	0,81	0,07
1398,91	1399,82	1399,79	0,90	0,87	0,03
1498,85	1499,91	1499,86	1,09	1,05	0,04
1600,00	1601,13	1601,13	1,13	1,14	-0,01
1698,80	1699,83	1700,16	1,03	1,36	-0,32
1798,13	1799,48		1,33		

Table 2.6: Summary of results from RISE, JV and DFM.

Comparing the measurements from JV and DFM to those from RISE show that they measure higher than the RISE LP5 measurements, as can be seen in Figure 2.11.

Figure 2.11: Temperature deviation of the measurements of DFM and JV compared to RISE.

As the blackbody cavity has an opening of Ø5 mm it is not expected to be related to the SSE correction, and might instead be attributed to different spot sizes being more susceptible to inhomogeneity of the radiation from the blackbody.

Comparing the JV measurements and the DFM measurements directly (Figure 2.12) show that they agree quite well over the scale.

Figure 2.12: Difference between the JV measurements and the DFM measurements calculated for each temperature measurement with the RISE LP5.

3 Comparison between SMU and CMI

The following section describes the comparison between SMU and CMI.

3.1 Introduction

The original plan for SMU was to compare its new scale with the ITS-90 scale realised at LNE from 1000 °C to 1400 °C. Due to technical and time limitations on both sides (SMU and LNE), the reference institute was changed to CMI and the temperature range was modified to 962 °C – 1300 °C.

3.2 Internal comparison at SMU

This section describes the “internal comparison” of the established temperature scale (ITS-90) with the newly developed temperature scale (Sakuma-Hattori).

ITS-90 realisation at SMU

Setup:

Standard radiant thermometer: Chino IR-RST65H. Detecting element: Silicon Photodiode. Nominal wavelength 650 nm. Measuring range: 1000 °C to 3000 °C in 3 step selection. Distance factor 650 (φ 1,1 mm at 800 mm). Output: Radiation luminance: 0 to 10 V DC (with zero adjustment). SN: IS-0239C0001

Fixed point: Isotech Silver FP (Ag) 998-06-00E SN: 198, (cavity size 10 mm x 90 mm). Ingot mass weight around 0,6 kg.

Furnace for fixed point: Isotech Oberon R426 (with Na heatpipe). Temperature range: 450 °C to 1100 °C.

Device to measure output signal from standard radiation thermometer: Multimeter 34420A Nanovolt/Micro-Ohm Meter. 2 channels. 7½ digit resolution.

Setup for inert atmosphere: Argon 99,999 % (Messer) with flowmeter Kytola LH-GS23HR (0,1 L/min to 1 L/min).

PC + HP Vee software to readings output signal from SMU Chino via multimeter.

The spectral response for the SMU Chino was measured at SMU (photometry and radiometry department).

Results from measurements on a silver fixed-point are shown in Table 3.1 Table 3.2 as well as in Figure 3.3. The experimental setup can be seen in Figure 3.1 Figure 3.2

The mean wavelength to Chino pyrometer λ_0 ((580 to 720) nm) / nm*	The standard deviation of the spectral responsivity σ ((580 to 720) nm) / nm*	σ^2 / nm
651,05	4,851	23,53

Table 3.1: * Formula (5) and (6) p. 7/17 from: Guide to the Realization of the ITS-90 Radiation Thermometry. The measurement using the pyrometer (SMU Chino) in FP Ag was perform according ITS-90 document and the setup describe above.

FP	Temp / K	Chino raw signal / mV	multimeter corr. / mV	dark signal corr. / mV	SSE corr. / mV	emiss. corr. / mV	temperature drop corr. / mV	Chino final signal / mV
Ag	1234,93	4,46512	-0,0001	-0,013	0,0018	0,0022	0,0017	4,48391

Table 3.2: Measurements of the Ag fixed-point.

Figure 3.1: Setup for measurement in FP.

Figure 3.2: Schematic picture position FP in furnace and pyrometer alignment.

Figure 3.3: Example of one of the plateaus for the SMU Chino pyrometer measurement in Ag FP.

New equipment at SMU (for Sakuma- Hattori method)

The 9 fixed and eutectic points the SMU made (1x Ag, 1x Au, 2x Cu, 1x Fe-C, 2x Co-C, 2x Pd-C) were realized in the 2 furnaces shown in Table 3.3.

Furnace	Isotech Oberon	Vecstar
Temperature range	Up to 1100 °C	Up to 1550 °C
Heating zones	One / Sodium heatpipe	One zone
Vacuuming (before)	No	Yes
FP	Ag, Au, Cu	Fe-C, Co-C, Pd-C

Table 3.3: Furnaces used at SMU for fixed-point realisations.

The fixed points were tested several times in the furnaces and Table 3.4 below is the average value for them. Note that the Co-C FP was removed from table due to very poor plateaux.

FPs	Chino raw signal / mV	multimeter corr. / mV	dark signal corr. / mV	SSE corr. / mV	emiss. corr. / mV	temperature drop corr. / mV	Chino final signal / mV
Ag1	4,4529	-0,0001	-0,0300	0,0000	0,0013	0,0003	4,48456
Au1	17,6040	-0,0002	-0,0309	0,0000	0,0053	0,0012	17,64155
Cu2	22,5695	-0,0003	-0,0130	0,0000	0,0068	0,0016	22,59113
Fe-C1	49,5631	-0,0006	-0,0130	0,0000	0,0148	0,0038	49,59533
Pd-C2	962,9872	0,0481	-0,0132	0,0000	0,2885	0,1144	963,35514

Table 3.4: Results from fixed-point measurements.

The comparisons of the newly developed temperature scale realizations against ITS-90

The comparison of the ITS-90 realization against several fixed-points is shown in Table 3.5 below. Each temperature difference ($t_{90} - t_{nom}$) is well within the expanded uncertainty to each fixed-point, and hence we conclude that the new fixed-points and the measurement setup are good.

FP	t_{nom} [°C]	Chino final signal [mV]	t_{90} [°C]	$t_{90} - t_{nom}$ [°C]	U_{t90} [°C] (k=2)
Ag1	961,78	4,48456	961,82	0,04	0,32
Au1	1064,18	17,64155	1064,27	0,09	0,36
Cu2	1084,62	22,59113	1084,61	-0,01	0,36
Fe-C1	1153,77	49,59533	1153,60	-0,17	0,39
Pd-C2	1491,90	963,35514	1491,88	-0,02	0,54

Table 3.5: * t_{90} was calculated by formula (12) p. 9/17 from: Guide to the Realization of the ITS-90 Radiation Thermometry.

The second option for an ITS-90 realization comparison is to compare it against the Sakuma-Hattori calculation. In the Multifix calculator v0.9.14 software (created by TUBITAK) the Sakuma-Hattori coefficients (A, B, C) are calculated using fixed-points from Ag to Pd-C. The following values were acquired when t_{nom} in K for fixed-points were used together with the output signal from the chino pyrometer.

Sakuma Hattori coefficients		
A	647,1727833	nm
B	3319,112091	nm.K
C	274263983,6	mV

$$T = \frac{c_2}{A * \ln\left(\frac{c}{U_{pyr}} + 1\right)} - \frac{B}{A}$$

When the output signal from the chino is converted to temperature for the fixed-points and the values are compared to those calculated by ITS-90, the differences can be seen in Table 3.6 below. The results are also in a scale of the expanded uncertainty, so that in the future both the ITS-90 or multi fixed points method can be used.

FP	t_{nom} [°C]	t_{90} [°C]	t_{SAKUMA} [°C]	$t_{SAKUMA} - t_{90}$ [°C]
Ag1	961,78	961,82	961,71	-0,11
Au1	1064,18	1064,27	1064,27	0,00
Cu2	1084,62	1084,61	1084,62	0,01
Fe-C1	1153,77	1153,60	1153,65	0,06
Pd-C2	1491,90	1491,88	1491,88	0,00

Table 3.6: Comparison of temperatures.

Conclusion: The comparison results presented in Table 3.6 demonstrate that the newly developed temperature scale is sufficient for SMU.

3.3 SMU vs. CMI compare

SMU and CMI compared the calibration of their interpolating instruments (Sakuma-Hattori method / temperature scale realization) with the ITS-90 scale realised at CMI from 962 °C to 1300 °C. The measurements were carried out at the SMU laboratory in November 2025. A Sensotherm CS1500S blackbody was used as the temperature source for the following temperatures: (962; 1100 and 1300) °C.

The measuring distance for the Chino and LP5 pyrometers were 80 cm, and the setup can be seen in Figure 3.4.

Figure 3.4: Arrangement of the thermometers.

In Table 3.7 below are the results from the measurements.

CMI - LP5 [°C]	$U_{\text{CMI}} (k=2)$ [°C]	SMU - Chino/Sakum [°C]	$U_{\text{SMU}} (k=2)$ [°C]	Chino - LP5 [°C]
962,86	1,10	962,71	1,50	-0,15
1100,93	1,10	1100,98	1,60	0,05
1301,50	1,20	1301,91	1,70	0,41

Table 3.7: Results from measurements.

Conclusion: The comparison results presented in the table above demonstrate that the newly developed temperature scale is sufficient for SMU (the difference between SMU and CMI lies within their expanded uncertainties).

4 TUBITAK

4.1 Introduction

This report presents the results of the comparison between the newly developed TÜBİTAK UME interpolation pyrometer (designated TSP2) and the laboratory's ITS-90 scale as established using the LP5 linear pyrometer (KE Technologie GmbH). The work is carried out within the framework of the European Partnership on Metrology project 22RPT03 MultiFixRad ("Improving the Realisation of the Kelvin by Multiple Fixed Point Radiation Thermometry"), co-financed from the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Program and by the Participating States.

The primary objective of this deliverable is to evaluate the performance of the newly developed interpolation instrument, calibrated in task A3.2.2 according to the in-house procedure for ITS-90 scale realisation, by

comparing it directly against the laboratory's ITS-90 scale established using the LP5 linear pyrometer over the temperature range from 960 °C to 2500 °C.

The TSP2 is a modified radiation thermometer interpolation device employing a narrow-band interference filter centred at 900 nm (± 15 nm bandwidth), equipped with a wide-area 100 mm² silicon photodetector. The instrument was designed to serve as a low-cost, high-stability device for primary thermometry, reducing reliance on absolute calibration while strengthening the link between ITS-90 and the mise en pratique for the definition of the kelvin (MeP-K).

4.2 Instrumentation

TSP2 Interpolation Pyrometer

The TSP2 (pictured in Figure 4.1) is the newly constructed interpolation radiation thermometer developed at TÜBİTAK UME. Its key characteristics are as follows:

- Spectral range: narrow-band filter at central wavelength 900 nm
- Detector: large-area (100 mm²) silicon photodetector
- Calibration fixed points: Cu (1084.62 °C), Fe-C, Co-C, Ru-C, Re-C, and WC-C
- Operating mode: relative-radiometric interpolation between fixed points

The instrument was rigorously characterized in terms of linearity, gain ratio behavior, Size-of-Source Effect (SSE), and environmental sensitivity prior to use in scale realization. The TSP2 signal was found to be essentially unaffected by ambient environmental conditions due to its special head design.

Figure 4.1: TSP2 pyrometer positioned in front of a blackbody source.

LP5 Linear Pyrometer

The LP5 (pictured in Figure 4.2) is a commercial linear pyrometer manufactured by KE Technologie GmbH. It constitutes TÜBİTAK UME's primary ITS-90 scale realisation instrument and serves as the reference standard in this comparison. The LP5 employs active cooling capable of maintaining detector temperature stability within ± 0.1 K. Its spectral responsivity is centred near 650 nm, as determined from relative spectral responsivity measurements performed at different signal levels.

Figure 4.2: LP5 linear pyrometer positioned in front of a blackbody source.

Spectral Responsivity

The relative spectral responsivity of both instruments was characterised using a monochromator-based setup. The TSP2 shows a well-defined bandpass centred at approximately 900 nm with minimal out-of-band transmission across the measured range of 800–1000 nm, see Figure 4.3. The LP5 exhibits a narrow responsivity peak near 650 nm with good repeatability, see Figure 4.4. Each spectral responsivity is fit for rectangular distribution, see information in Table 4.1.

Figure 4.3: TSP2 spectral responsivity measured at different signal levels (800–1000 nm).

Figure 4.4: LP5 spectral responsivity measured at different signal levels (400–1100 nm).

Interpolation Device	Mean Wavelength (λ_0 , nm)	Standard Deviation (σ , nm, rectangular distribution)
LP5	650.57	3.96
TSP2	907.26	9.96

Table 4.1: Interpolation devices spectral parameters.

4.3 Experimental Setup and Measurement Conditions

Both radiation thermometers were compared under identical viewing geometry using high-precision variable-temperature blackbody source:

- BB3500 conical cavity: operating range 1500–3000 K, 35 mm aperture

Both instruments were calibrated consecutively at the Cu fixed point (1084.62 °C), ensuring identical traceability, see Figure 4.5. Short-term drift monitoring was performed by periodically re-realising the Cu fixed point throughout the measurement campaign. The comparison was then extended across five eutectic high-temperature fixed points (HTFPs): Fe-C, Co-C, Ru-C, Re-C, and WC-C.

Figure 4.5: LP5 and TSP2 eutectic fixed-point realisation

4.4 Instrument Characterisation

Size-of-Source Effect

The Size-of-Source Effect (SSE) was characterized using the indirect method. A quartz plate containing a central black cavity (3 mm diameter) was positioned at the exit port of an integrating sphere. Measurements were performed with varying aperture diameters to quantify the fractional signal contribution from outside the nominal target area.

Results indicate that the LP5 SSE shows no significant change from its initial characterisation at time of purchase, confirming long-term optical stability. The experimental setup and results can be seen in Figure 4.6Figure 4.7. For TSP2, a newly constructed SSE measurement system was developed, and the results demonstrate an improvement compared to earlier measurements, attributed to the wide-area detector design which reduces the sensitivity to source spatial non-uniformity. The experimental setup and results can be seen in Figure 4.8Figure 4.9.

Figure 4.6: SSE measurement setup for LP5.

Figure 4.7: SSE measurement results for LP5.

Figure 4.8: SSE measurement setup for TSP2

Figure 4.9: SSE measurement results for TSP2.

Linearity Measurements

The linearity of both pyrometers was evaluated using the radiance-doubling method. In this method, the non-linearity deviation L is computed as:

$$L_{AB} = \frac{I_{AB} - I_{dark}}{I_A + I_B - 2I_{dark}}$$

Here I_{dark} is the corresponding dark signal, I_{AB} denotes the signal measured when both light sources are on, and I_A and I_B is the signal measured when each light source is individually activated. This measurement is repeated with varying apertures. The radiance-doubling technique employs two independent light sources (tungsten lamps) powered by stabilised supplies and monitored via a beam splitter and shunt resistor arrangement. Linearity system is still in working progress. The experimental setup is seen in Figure 4.10 and the results in Figure 4.11.

Figure 4.10: Linearity measurement setup for both LP5 and TSP2

Figure 4.11: Linearity measurement results for both LP5 and TSP2

At this study linearity correction is not applied only considered in uncertainty budget.

Environmental Sensitivity

Environmental sensitivity was evaluated by varying the ambient temperature inside a climate-controlled chamber (Figure 4.12) between 10 °C, 23 °C, and 40 °C at constant relative humidity and fixed source radiance. Measurements were performed at multiple signal levels and aperture sizes.

The TSP2 signal was found to be barely affected by environmental conditions. The LP5 relies on active cooling to maintain detector temperature stable within ± 0.1 K of its set point, which also provides good environmental robustness.

Figure 4.12: Environmental sensitivity measurement setup showing the TSP2 in a temperature-controlled chamber.

4.5 Fixed-Point Calibration and ITS-90 Scale Realisation

LP5

Both instruments were calibrated using the Cu fixed point as the primary reference ($T_{90} = 1357.77$ K, $t_{90} = 1084.62$ °C). The plateau determination, short-term drift monitoring, and repeatability were assessed across multiple freeze and melt cycles, see Figure 4.13. The expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$) for the Cu calibration is 0.09 °C. The results from the copper measurements can be seen in Table 4.2 and the Sakuma-Hattori coefficients in Table 4.3.

Figure 4.13: Cu fixed-point plateau measured with LP5 showing multiple freeze cycles with insets of full melting range and plateau detail.

	Temp	LP5 raw signal	Dark signal corr.	LP5 signal	SSE corr.	Emiss. corr.	Temperature drop corr.	LP5 final signal
	[K]	[A]	[A]	[A]	[A]	[A]	[A]	[A]
Cu	1357.77	2.6746e-10	-4.0119E-14	2.6742e-10	-1.9581E-14	9.9700E-14	3.8000E-15	2.6750E-10

Table 4.2: LP5 Copper fixed-point measurement results.

Coefficients	Value
a	6.498310e-01
b	1.361231e+00
c	3.150964e-03
c2	14388

Table 4.3: LP5 Sakuma-Hattori Coefficients.

The uncertainty budget for the Cu fixed-point calibration is summarised in Table 4.4, and for eutectic fixed-points in Table 4.5.

Source of Uncertainty	Contribution / °C (at 1084.62 °C)
Impurity	0.012
Emissivity	0.005
Temperature drop	0.004
Cu plateau determination	0.007
Repeatability	0.010
Wavelength	0.000
Short-time drift	0.006
Out-of-band transmission	0.000
Size-of-source effect	0.003
Non-linearity	0.038
Environmental conditions	0.010
Expanded Uncertainty U (k=2)	0.09

Table 4.4: Uncertainty budget for Cu fixed-point calibration of LP5.

Uncertainty component	Type	Fe-C	Co-C	Ru-C	Re-C	WC-C
Gain Ratio	Systematic	0.009	0.012	0.022	0.035	0.041
Calibration of the radiation thermometer	Systematic	0.066	0.102	0.233	0.411	0.562
Linearity of radiation thermometer	Systematic	0.014	0.019	0.034	0.053	0.062
Ambient Temperature	Random	0.001	0.001	0.002	0.004	0.004
The drift of the radiation thermometer	Systematic	0.006	0.009	0.014	0.02	0.025
SSE (combined instrument and source uniformity)	Systematic	0.018	0.021	0.045	0.071	0.083
Alignment of radiation thermometer	Systematic	0.018	0.021	0.045	0.071	0.083
Determination of POI	Random	0.035	0.006	0.003	0.009	0.009
Stability of source	Random	0.031	0.006	0.005	0.004	0.004
Emissivity	Systematic	0.014	0.020	0.034	0.052	0.062
Temperature Drop	Systematic	0.002	0.003	0.006	0.021	0.026
Expanded Uncertainty, k, (k = 2)		0.18	0.22	0.50	0.86	1.17

Table 4.5: Uncertainty budget for Eutectic fixed-points calibration of LP5

Following the Cu calibration, the LP5 were used to realize the ITS-90 scale at five eutectic fixed points. Table 4.6 presents the measured radiance signals, temperatures and associated uncertainty at each fixed point for LP5.

Fixed Point	Assigned Thermodynamic T [K]	U(T(K)), (k = 2)	LP5 Signal [A]	LP5 T ₉₀ [K]	T-T ₉₀ [K]	Expanded Uncertainty, U(k = 2)
Fe-C	1426.92	0.16	5.8892E-10	1426.93	-0.01	0.18
Co-C	1597.39	0.13	3.0737E-09	1597.27	0.12	0.22
Ru-C	2226.99	0.24	1.5363E-07	2226.35	0.64	0.50
Re-C	2747.84	0.35	1.0090E-06	2746.77	1.07	0.86
WC-C	3020.85	0.40	2.0888E-06	3019.53	1.32	1.17

Table 4.6: T-T90 measurement results of LP5.

The fixed-point plateau realisations for LP5 at the Fe-C, Co-C, Re-C, and WC-C fixed-points are presented in Figure 4.14 - Figure 4.18 below.

Figure 4.14: Fe-C fixed-point plateaus.

Figure 4.15: Co-C fixed-point plateaus.

Figure 4.16: Ru-C fixed-point plateaus.

Figure 4.17: Re-C fixed-point plateaus.

Figure 4.18: WC-C fixed-point plateaus.

TSP2

The plateau determination, short-term drift monitoring, and repeatability were assessed across multiple freeze and melt cycles (Figure 4.19). The expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$) for the Cu calibration is $0.43\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The results from the copper measurements can be seen in Table 4.7 and the Sakuma-Hattori coefficients in Table 4.8.

Figure 4.19: Cu fixed-point plateau measured with TSP2 showing multiple freeze cycles.

	Temp / K	TSP2 raw signal [V]	dark signal corr. [V]	TSP2 Gain	Gain / dark corrected signal	SSE corr. [V]	emiss. corr.	temperature drop corr -	TSP2 final signal
Cu	1357.77	5.303722	8.259922E-05	99844870	5.303805	-2.252658E-10	-1.58702E-11	8.01320E-13	5.291026E-08

Table 4.7: TSP2 Copper fixed-point measurement results.

Coefficients	Value
a	9.067326e-01
b	6.999288e-01
c	6.254003e-03
c2	14388

Table 4.8: TSP2 Sakuma-Hattori Coefficients.

The uncertainties for the copper fixed-point (Table 4.9), and for the eutectic (Table 4.10) are shown below, as well as $T-T_{90}$ for the TSP2 (Table 4.11).

Source of Uncertainty	Contribution / $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (at $1084.62\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$)
Impurity	0.012
Emissivity	0.011
Temperature drop	0.004
Cu plateau determination	0.010
Repeatability	0.010
Wavelength	0.000
Short-time drift	0.120
Out-of-band transmission	0.000
Size-of-source effect	0.134
Non-linearity	0.093
Gain Ratios	0.067
Expanded Uncertainty U (k=2)	0.43

Table 4.9: Uncertainty budget for Cu fixed-point calibration of TSP2.

Uncertainty component	Type	Fe-C	Co-C
Gain Ratio	Systematic	0.074	0.092
Linearity of radiation thermometer	Systematic	0.102	0.128
Ambient Temperature	Random	0.001	0.002
The drift of the radiation thermometer	Systematic	0.133	0.166
SSE (combined instrument and source uniformity)	Systematic	0.148	0.185
Alignment of radiation thermometer	Systematic	0.052	0.078
Determination of POI	Random	0.052	0.078
Stability of source	Random	0.062	0.092
Emissivity	Systematic	0.014	0.018
Temperature Drop	Systematic	0.01	0.012
Expanded Uncertainty, k, (k = 2)		0.51	0.66

Table 4.10: Uncertainty budget for Eutectic fixed-points calibration of TSP2.

Fixed Point	Assigned Thermodynamic T(K)	U(T(K)), (k=2)	TSP2 Signal [A]	TSP2 T ₉₀ (K)	T-T ₉₀ (K)	Expanded Uncertainty (k = 2)
Fe-C	1426.92	0.16	9.38220E-08	1427.32	-0.40	0.51
Co-C	1597.39	0.13	3.07300E-07	1598.03	-0.64	0.66

Table 4.11: T-T₉₀ measurement results of TSP2.

These values are based on the measurements of several plateaus, as seen in Figure 4.20Figure 4.21.

Figure 4.20: Fe-C fixed-point plateaus.

Figure 4.21: Co-C fixed-point plateaus.

4.6 Comparison of TSP2 and LP5

A direct comparison of the temperature readings between TSP2 and LP5 was performed over the range 1000 °C to 1600 °C using the blackbody source Land 1600. Both instruments were operated simultaneously viewing the same blackbody target, with temperatures stepped in 100 °C increments. The experimental setup can be seen in Figure 4.22.

Figure 4.22: Comparison of LP5 and TSP2 against dummy cell.

The temperature differences (LP5 – TSP2) at each set point from 1000 °C to 1600 °C are tabulated in Table 4.12.

LP5 / °C	$U(k=2)$ / °C	TSP2/Sakuma / °C	$U(k=2)$ / °C	TSP – LP5 / °C
1000.84	0.08	1000.81	0.37	-0.03
1100.39	0.10	1100.66	0.44	0.27
1199.83	0.19	1199.99	0.53	0.15
1300.48	0.23	1300.13	0.62	0.35
1400.81	0.26	1400.25	0.72	0.56
1500.58	0.30	1499.97	0.82	0.61
1600.45	0.34	1599.62	0.93	0.83

Table 4.12: ITS-90 uncertainty budget for TSP2 at selected fixed points.

5 Conclusion

This report has presented work done in the MultiFixRad project and the efforts by some project partners to directly compare the newly developed temperature scale realisations with existing implementations of the ITS-90. The main comparison work in the project is the inter-consortium ILC K-10, which is ongoing at the time of writing.

Above the freezing point of silver (1235 K) the ITS-90 is realised using Planck's law in the ratio form, using a blackbody at the freezing point of pure Ag, Au or Cu as its reference temperature, i.e. it prescribes an extrapolation from a single fixed point. As a consequence, ITS-90 requires detailed knowledge of the pyrometer, in particular its linearity, and only a few of the participants currently have suitable equipment. Less experienced NMI/DIs who did not have the ITS-90 scale realisation capability, worked with project participants which employed existing pyrometric implementations of the ITS-90. The comparisons were performed from 960 °C to 2500 °C, but with specific ranges for each participant as detailed in the activity descriptions.

RISE, SMU, CMI and TUBITAK had equipment to realise the ITS-90. In this work, SMU compared their fixed point based scale to both the CMI and their own implementation of the ITS-90, TUBITAK compared with their own implementation of the ITS-90, while DFM and JV compared their scales to the ITS-90 implementation at RISE.

In the nordic comparison between JV, DFM and RISE there was a temperature dependent difference between the ITS-90 temperatures from RISEs LP5 pyrometer and the devices of JV and DFM. The difference was approximately linear in temperature, reaching slightly above 1.3 °C at the highest temperature of 1800 °C. However, the uncertainty in the difference is similar in magnitude. The main issue with that comparison is the non-isothermal cavity, which leads to quite large corrections. It also means that the radiation thermometers are quite sensitive to the field of view. While we have spent some effort to model the effects of the temperature inhomogeneity, the magnitude of the corrections are substantial and could introduce some uncertainty contributions we have not properly taken into account.

Similarly, a central European comparison was performed by SMU, comparing the calibration of their interpolating instruments with the ITS-90 scale realised at CMI from 962 °C to 1300 °C. The difference was below 0.4 °C, again within uncertainty.

TUBITAK has also performed a comparison between the pyrometer they have developed and the ITS-90 scale implementation they have at the NMI. The difference remained below 0.9 °C at all temperatures, again within uncertainty. Similarly to the case in the Nordic comparison the deviation seemingly followed a linear trend in temperature. While this has not been investigated further, there seems to be a systematic bias, similar in magnitude and trend, across the three comparisons performed. This could point to some overlooked effect in the implementations of the new scales.